

AI-Driven Approaches to Plastic and Chemical Pollutant Monitoring in Wastewater Treatment: A Case Study

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Abstract:

Plastic particles and chemical pollutants have become a significant contaminant in wastewater system, threatening the wellbeing of human health and aquatic ecosystem. These pollutants can accumulate in waterbodies, in fishes and many other aquatic organisms, and may enter the food chain. Conventional methods for monitoring such pollutants is time consuming, labour-intensive and lack real-time accuracy, making them inappropriate prolonged environment monitoring. This case study explores how AI-driven systems are enhancing the identification and detection of plastic and chemical pollutant and also helps in wastewater treatment processes. Interpretation of the existing results, shows how intelligent monitoring tools effectively help in detecting contaminants, improve accuracy and strength anticipatory analysis for pollution control. The combination of these technologies not only speed up the assessment process but also provide critical insight into the dynamic of pollutant dispersion and impact on ecosystem health.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), Plastic pollutants, Chemical contaminants, Aquatic ecosystem, Pollution detection

Introduction:

Water is the key resource for human survival, industrial operations and for aquatic organisms, yet it faces extreme threats due to toxic pollutants, natural phenomenon and several human activities (Ahmad, *et al.*, 2022). Rapidly expanding global population, growing urbanization, industrialization and widespread impact of climate change have intensified water pollution and contributed to ecological damage (Halepoto, *et al.*, 2022; Ahmad, *et al.*, 2022; Hamaideh A., *et al.*, 2024). All these factors together cause great stress and pressure on water resources resulting in both qualitative and quantitative restrictions (Liu J., *et al.*, 2017). The limited availability of potable water is a critical concern in developing nation. (Rafiei Sardooi, *et al.*, 2024). Increased water demand of many industrial sectors leads to environmental degradation and ecosystem threat via discharge of toxic and non-biodegradable effluents and particles (Karthikeyan, *et al.*, 2017). Manufacturing related microplastic pollution has become a critical

environmental problem (Rezania, *et al.*, 2018; Devipriya, *et al.*, 2025).

To address these growing pollution-related challenges in real-world water systems, many practical and efficient techniques are increasingly being enhanced by artificial intelligence (AI) (Marr *et al.*, 2019; Xu Y. *et al.*, 2021). Technologies based on AI are easy to use, operate quickly, and provide sufficient accuracy without requiring extensive physical expertise (Dwivedi Y. K. *et al.*, 2021).

In recent years, in a field of wastewater treatment AI techniques has emerge a revolutionary approach in this field (Safeer *et al.*, 2022). AI comprises of machine learning (ML), neural networks, and many other computational methods, that enable us to analyze vast dataset, to evaluate possible outcome in real time (Wang *et al.*, 2023). This has ability to revolutionize how waste water treatment plants (WWTPs) operate, providing a smart solution to challenging problems (Nagpal, *et al.*, 2024). The bibliometric report clearly indicates the relationship between AI and water/wastewater

treatment with various treatment strategies to reduce water pollution and greenhouse gases (Mathaba, M., *et al.*, 2023).

Along with microplastic contamination, chemical pollution originating from wastewater discharges poses a serious threat to water quality. Chemical pollutants such as suspended solids, heavy metals, nutrients, and organic compounds are commonly removed through coagulation–flocculation processes, which play a crucial role in both drinking water and wastewater treatment (Matviichuk, 2024; Kote & Wadkar, 2019). Determining the optimal coagulant dose under fluctuating influent conditions is complex due to the highly non-linear interactions between water quality parameters such as pH, turbidity, conductivity, and pollutant concentration (Matviichuk, 2024; Jin *et al.*, 2025). Conventional approaches, including jar tests and operator-based control, are time-consuming and often result in over- or under-dosing of chemicals, which can reduce treatment efficiency, increase chemical consumption, and adversely affect sludge production and effluent quality (Nagpal *et al.*, 2024; Zou *et al.*, 2025).

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) have been widely applied to address these challenges due to their strong capability to model complex, non-linear relationships in treatment processes. Previous studies have demonstrated that ANN-based models can accurately predict optimal coagulant and disinfectant dosages, improve treatment efficiency, reduce chemical consumption, and support real-time decision-making in water treatment plants (Kote & Wadkar, 2019; Matviichuk, 2024; Jin *et al.*, 2025).

This technique is widespread adopted in WWTPs due to their cost serving ability (Nagpal, *et al.*, 2024).

Chemical pollutants in wastewater are usually monitored by using numerical physicochemical and sensor-based parameters like PH, COD, BOD and metal concentration. AI system of artificial neural networks (ANNs) is efficient for such kind of applications as they can model complex, many nonlinear relationships between

input variable and pollutant level. While microplastic particles are clearly visible contaminants whose classification and identifications are depends on image features like shape, size and surface textures. Convolution neural networks (CNNs) which are typically design for imaged based analysis, that facilities automatic features extraction and accurate classification of microplastic particles. Therefore, using ANN based model for chemical pollutant identification and CNN based architectures for plastic particles monitoring represent a well-structured plan for evaluation of toxic chemical and plastic particles.

Review Framework and Case Study Selection:

The present study adopts a structured, review-based case study approach to examine the application of artificial intelligence techniques in environmental monitoring and wastewater treatment. Rather than reporting original experimental work, the focus is placed on critically analysing and synthesising evidence from previously published, peer-reviewed studies. This approach allows for a systematic understanding of how AI-driven methods have been applied to address challenges related to microplastic detection, chemical pollutant monitoring, and treatment process optimisation in complex treatment environments.

The selection of case studies was guided by clearly defined inclusion criteria to ensure both relevance and scientific quality. Only peer-reviewed journal articles were considered, with emphasis placed on studies that explicitly applied artificial intelligence techniques—such as convolutional neural networks and artificial neural networks—to water or wastewater treatment applications. Additional consideration was given to the clarity of methodological reporting, the availability of performance evaluation metrics, and the practical relevance of the study outcomes to environmental monitoring or chemical process control.

Case Study Analysis:

Case Study 1:

Background and Rationale:

The case study is based on the research article titled “Automated micro-plastic detection and classification using deep convolution neural network pre-trained models and transfer learning” by K. Devipriya *et al.*, published in the journal AIP Advances in 2025. The researcher uses many deep CNN architectures to detect or classify the microplastic particles into different beads, fibers and fragments samples.

This research work examines an AI-Driven approach in which many CNN-Based pre-trained models were applied for automated classification and detection of microplastic particles using image data, categorizing them into beads, fibers and fragment samples. The study clearly indicated that how transfer learning considerably enhances microplastic monitoring by limiting manual effort and improving classification accuracy.

Data Source and Nature of Study:

The study is Data Driven and experimental in nature as this involved validation, model training and performance comparison using real image data.

All the data set was divided into training and testing subsets to evaluate model generalization. Some image processing techniques like resizing and normalization were applied to ensure compatibility with CNN input requirements.

Figure 1. AI-based workflow for microplastic detection.

AI Methodology: CNN based approach:

CNN techniques are particularly suitable for microplastic detection because they can automatically capture many spatial features such as shape, size, edge and texture from the image datasets.

To enhance the efficiency and accuracy the researcher adopted a transfer learning approach in which many pre-trained models on large image datasets were fine-tuned for microplastic classification.

Figure 2. Pre-trained CNN architectures used for microplastic detection

Case Study Overview and Assessment:

The analysis of all five pre-trained models shows notable differences in their effectiveness for microplastic particle detection.

Case study: 2

Background and Rationale:

This case study draws on the work of Matviichuk (2024), which investigates ANN-based optimisation of coagulant dosing in industrial wastewater treatment. Industrial wastewater systems face increasing challenges due to variable influent quality, complex pollutants, and stricter discharge standards. While coagulation–flocculation is essential for removing turbidity and suspended solids, conventional dosing methods such as jar tests and operator control often lack adaptability under dynamic conditions.

Advances in artificial intelligence have enabled data-driven treatment strategies, with artificial neural networks (ANNs) widely used to model non-linear relationships between water quality parameters and treatment performance ((Hameed & Al-Saadi, 2004; Nagpal *et al.*, 2024). The analysed study serves as a representative example of ANN-based coagulant dosing optimisation, illustrating both the potential and limitations of ANN-driven wastewater treatment approaches.

Methodological Overview:

The study employed a multilayer perceptron (MLP) ANN model to predict the optimal coagulant dose based on key wastewater parameters such as pH, turbidity, and electrical conductivity. Historical operational data were collected from industrial wastewater treatment facilities were used to train, validate, and test the model.

Figure 3. Methodological Framework for ANN-Based Coagulant Dosing

This methodology allows the ANN to adapt to changing wastewater conditions, providing real-time recommendations that improve treatment outcomes while reducing chemical usage.

ANN-Based Modelling Approach:

The study specifically utilized a multilayer perceptron (MLP) network, which is one of the most widely applied ANN architectures in process engineering, due to its robustness and suitability for modelling non-linear treatment processes.

The MLP model consisted of:

Figure 4. ANN Model Architecture for Coagulant Dose Prediction

The model was trained using historical datasets collected from industrial wastewater operations. Once trained, the ANN model could generalise to new, unseen data, providing accurate and adaptive predictions for coagulant dosing under varying wastewater conditions.

Figure 5. Conceptual Framework for ANN-Based Coagulant Dosing in Industrial Wastewater Treatment

The application of ANN technologies in this study demonstrated several advantages:

Non-linear Modelling: Captures complex relationships between multiple water quality parameters and coagulant demand that conventional linear methods cannot.

Real-Time Prediction: Supports continuous dosing adjustments in response to fluctuating influent characteristics.

Reduction of Manual Intervention: Minimises reliance on jar tests and operator experience, saving time and reducing errors.

Optimisation of Resources: Improves dosing efficiency, lowering chemical usage and operational costs.

Implications for Chemical Pollutant Monitoring:

ANN-based approach also offers valuable implications for chemical pollutant monitoring. Continuous analysis of water quality parameters such as turbidity and conductivity enables detection of abnormal influent conditions and real-time adjustment of coagulant dosing. This improves

treatment efficiency by reducing dosing errors, enhancing removal of particle-associated pollutants, and optimising chemical usage. While individual pollutants are not explicitly modelled, improved coagulation performance is expected to indirectly stabilise their removal, supporting a more predictive and adaptive wastewater management strategy.

Limitations and Research Gaps:

While the study demonstrates the potential of ANN models in optimising coagulant dosing, several limitations and areas for future research are identified:

Data Dependence: The model's accuracy depends on the quality and comprehensiveness of historical datasets. Sparse or inconsistent data may reduce predictive performance.

Generalizability: The model was developed for a specific industrial wastewater context; its direct application to other wastewater types may require retraining or adaptation.

Integration Challenges: Implementation requires real-time monitoring infrastructure and integration of AI models into plant control systems, which may be costly or complex.

Extended Pollutant Types: While the study focuses on coagulant dosing for chemical pollutants, integrating microplastic detection or other emerging contaminants remains an open research area.

Case Study Overview and Assessment:

This case study demonstrates the application of a feedforward MLP-based ANN for optimising coagulant dosing in industrial wastewater treatment under fluctuating influent conditions. Process variables such as pH, turbidity, and conductivity were used as model inputs due to their strong influence on coagulation behaviour. The results suggest that ANN-based models can support more responsive and consistent dosing strategies while reducing dependence on operator-driven control.

Conclusion:

The collective analysis of the case studies presented in this work shows the increasing relevance of artificial intelligence-based approaches in addressing key challenges in wastewater treatment and environmental pollutant monitoring. By covering applications ranging from deep learning-based microplastic detection to artificial neural network-driven optimisation of chemical dosing, the study illustrates how AI tools can address several limitations of conventional monitoring and control methods, which are often labour-intensive, time-consuming, and slow to respond to changing conditions.

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